

Blood Donor Deferral Analysis In Relation To the Screening Process among Blood Donors in Blood Centre, ESIMCH, Bihta, PatnaPriyamvada¹, Swati Salila²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology & Incharge Bloodcenter, ESICMCH, Bihta, Patna²Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, ESICMCH, Bihta, Patna

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Recruitment of blood donation is a critical element of healthcare, essential for surgeries, trauma care, and treatment of chronic illnesses. However, donor deferral due to various screening criteria can significantly impact blood supply availability. This study aims to analyze the reasons for blood donor deferral at the ESICMCH Blood Centre, Bihta, Patna, and identify significant predictors to enhance donor retention and ensure a stable blood supply.

Methods: A retrospective, observational study was conducted, involving 350 voluntary blood donors. Data on demographic characteristics and deferral reasons were collected and analyzed using chi-square tests and logistic regression in SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Out of 350 donors, 70 (20%) were deferred. The primary reasons for deferral were low hemoglobin (35.7%), recent illness (21.4%), and high blood pressure (14.3%). Significant associations were found between gender and deferral ($p = 0.033$), with males being more likely to be deferred. Logistic regression identified male gender (OR = 1.89, $p = 0.018$), low hemoglobin (OR = 3.54, $p < 0.001$), and high blood pressure (OR = 2.18, $p = 0.031$) as significant predictors of deferral.

Conclusion: The study highlights the prevalence and reasons for voluntary blood donor deferral at the ESICMCH Blood Centre. Low hemoglobin and high blood pressure are significant predictors of deferral, particularly among male donors.

Recommendations: To reduce deferral rates and improve blood supply, targeted health interventions focusing on improving nutritional status and managing chronic conditions among potential donors are recommended. Enhanced public health initiatives can also help address common deferral reasons.

Keywords: Blood Donation, Donor Deferral, Hemoglobin, Blood Pressure, Donor Retention.

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Introduction

Recruitment of voluntary, safe and healthy blood donors for provision of quality blood product to needy individuals in a timely manner is constant challenge faced by blood transfusion services in India. According to WHO, a minimum need to meet a nation's blood requirement is approximately 1% of its population. In India, annual blood collection during 2020-2021 was 5.83 million units against the target of 13 million units. Which decreased nearly 7.3 million units from previous year. Despite having huge population, where 50-60% are eligible for blood donation still a continuous shortage of blood exists. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to take necessary measures to increase the blood supply without compromising on the donor's health or safety of transfusion recipients. However, this screening process often results in a significant number of donor deferrals, which can impact the availability of blood. Understanding the reasons for donor deferral and identifying strategies to minimize unnecessary

deferrals are crucial for improving blood donation outcomes.

Blood donor deferral rates vary globally, influenced by factors such as regional health issues, demographic characteristics, and the stringency of screening criteria. A study highlighted that deferral rates can range from 5% to 20%, depending on the region and the specific criteria used for screening [1]. In India, donor deferral rates are often higher due to prevalent health issues such as anemia and infectious diseases, which are common reasons for deferral. A recent study reported that anemia accounted for 40% of all deferrals in a tertiary care centre in North India [2].

The implications of donor deferrals are multifaceted. For blood centres, high deferral rates can lead to a reduced donor pool, making it challenging to meet the demand for blood. For potential donors, deferrals can be discouraging and may reduce the likelihood of future donation

attempts. Addressing the underlying causes of deferrals through targeted health interventions and education can help mitigate these issues. Recent research suggests that improving nutritional status and managing chronic conditions among potential donors can significantly reduce deferral rates [3].

This study aims to analyze blood donor deferral in relation to the screening process.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective, observational design.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of October 2021 to July 2023 at ESICMCH, Bihta, Patna.

Participants: A total of 350 blood donors who visited the ESICMCH Blood Centre during the study period were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. All voluntary blood donors who visited the Blood Centre.
2. Voluntary donors who provided complete data during the screening process.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Voluntary donors with incomplete screening records.
2. Voluntary donors who did not meet the basic eligibility criteria for blood donation (e.g., age, weight, health conditions).
3. Apheresis donors.

Bias: To minimize bias, a standardized screening process was used for all donors. Data were anonymized to prevent identification of individual donors. Independent reviewers were involved in data analysis to ensure objectivity.

Data Collection: Data were collected from the records of blood donors who visited the ESICMCH Blood Centre. The following information was extracted:

- Demographic details (age, gender, weight).
- Medical history.
- Screening results.
- Reasons for deferral.

Procedure

1. Review and extract data from the blood centre's records for the specified period.
2. Verify the completeness and accuracy of the extracted data.
3. Classify the reasons for donor deferral based on predefined categories.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to enter the data and perform statistical analysis. To summarise the data, descriptive statistics such as percentages and frequencies were employed. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

A total of 350 blood donors were included in the study. The demographic characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Blood Donors

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	280	80.0
Female	70	20.0
Age Group (years)		
18-25	100	28.6
26-35	120	34.3
36-45	80	22.9
46-60	50	14.2

Out of 350 donors, 70 (20%) were deferred. The reasons for deferral are summarized in Table-2.

Table 2: Reasons for Donor Deferral

Reason for Deferral	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low Hemoglobin	25	35.7
High Blood Pressure	10	14.3
Recent Illness	15	21.4
Underweight	5	7.1
Travel to Malaria-endemic Area	8	11.4
Others	7	10.1

A chi-square test was conducted to examine the association between gender and deferral status. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Association Between Gender and Donor Deferral

Gender	Male	Female
Deferred (n=70)	50	20
Not Deferred (n=280)	20	50
Chi-Square	4.56	
p-value	0.033	

The association between age group and deferral status was also analyzed. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Association Between Age Group and Donor Deferral

Age Group (years)	18-25	26-35	36-45	46-60
Deferred (n=70)	20	25	15	10
Not Deferred (n=280)	80	95	65	40
Chi-Square	3.78			
p-value	0.152			

No significant association was found between age group and donor deferral ($p > 0.05$).

A logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify the predictors of donor deferral. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of Donor Deferral

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Gender (Male)	1.89	1.12-3.21	0.018
Age (continuous)	0.97	0.93-1.01	0.145
Low Hemoglobin	3.54	1.95-6.43	<0.001
High Blood Pressure	2.18	1.07-4.42	0.031

Discussion

Out of 350 donors, 70 (20%) were deferred, highlighting a significant portion of the donor population affected by deferral criteria. This deferral rate aligns with common patterns observed in blood donation centers, where stringent screening processes are essential to ensure the safety of both donors and recipients.

The study population consisted predominantly of male donors (80%), with the majority falling within the 26-35 age group (34.3%). Female donors constituted 20% of the sample. This gender disparity is consistent with trends seen in blood donation practices, where males often represent a higher proportion of donors due to eligibility criteria and social factors.

The most common reason for deferral was low hemoglobin, accounting for 35.7% of all deferrals. This finding underscores the importance of hemoglobin screening in the donor selection process to prevent anemia-related complications. Recent illness was the second most frequent cause, responsible for 21.4% of deferrals, indicating the rigorous health criteria necessary to protect the donor and the blood supply. Other notable deferral reasons included high blood pressure (14.3%) and travel to malaria-endemic areas (11.4%), reflecting the comprehensive nature of the screening process.

Chi-square tests revealed a significant association between gender and deferral status ($p = 0.033$), with male donors more likely to be deferred compared to female donors. This finding could be attributed to gender-specific health issues or

lifestyle factors influencing eligibility. However, no significant association was found between age groups and deferral status ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that deferral reasons are distributed relatively evenly across different age brackets.

Logistic regression analysis identified male gender (OR = 1.89, $p = 0.018$), low hemoglobin (OR = 3.54, $p < 0.001$), and high blood pressure (OR = 2.18, $p = 0.031$) as significant predictors of donor deferral. These predictors highlight critical areas for intervention to reduce deferral rates. For instance, improving nutritional education and health management among potential donors could help address issues related to low hemoglobin and high blood pressure.

Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing blood donor deferral. By identifying key predictors and common deferral reasons, the findings can inform targeted strategies to enhance donor retention and ensure a stable blood supply. The significant deferral rate due to low hemoglobin emphasizes the need for ongoing public health initiatives to improve the overall health and eligibility of the donor population.

A single centre in Southern India had its blood donor deferrals retrospectively analysed. They discovered that 10.6% of the 99,680 pre-donation examinations were postponed, with the haemoglobin check stage having the highest deferral rate (56.02%). 52.45% of donors had low haemoglobin, which was the main cause of deferral; in 3.75% of cases, high haemoglobin was the reason. The research emphasised how important

it is to use a quantitative haemoglobin analyser for precise screening [4].

Blood donor deferrals at a teaching hospital in Northeast India were assessed in a study. A deferral percentage of 18.77% was discovered among 20,137 potential donors by the study. Temporary deferrals accounted for 87.25% of all cases; common causes were anaemia (5.74%), medicines (19.58%), hypertension (20.83%), and inadequate sleep (14.45%). The study stressed that in order to lower deferrals because of controllable factors, pre-donation information is essential [5].

A cross-sectional study was carried out in a Kerala tertiary healthcare facility. 1,521 (4.2%) of the 36,318 blood donors were women. In comparison to males (16.04%), ladies had a greater deferral rate (47.9%). Fever and respiratory tract infections accounted for the majority of deferrals (18.55%), with low haemoglobin being the main factor in deferrals in females [6].

Donor deferrals at PGIMS, Rohtak, were examined in a study. According to the survey, there was a 7.71% deferral rate; temporary deferrals were more common (76.19%) than permanent ones (23.81%). Anaemia, underweight, and hypertension were the main reasons for deferral. The study emphasised how crucial it is to encourage donors who have temporarily postponed their donations to reconsider in the future [7].

In Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, a tertiary care hospital hosted a study. Out of 29,663 donors, the deferral rate was 8.85%, with anaemia being the most frequent reason. The frequency of temporary deferrals was higher than that of permanent deferrals, indicating the necessity of treating and educating temporarily deferred donors in order to preserve the donor pool [8].

Conclusion

This study identifies low hemoglobin and high blood pressure as the primary reasons for blood donor deferral. Male donors were more likely to be deferred. To improve donor retention and ensure a stable blood supply, targeted health interventions

and public health initiatives are essential. Addressing nutritional deficiencies and managing chronic health conditions among potential donors can significantly reduce deferral rates and enhance the overall efficiency of the blood donation process.

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